

ECONOMICS

THE IMPACT OF THE PANDEMIC ON ECONOMIC SECTORS AND WAYS TO ELIMINATE IT

Ibragimov B.

Doctor of Philosophy, Associate professor of the Tashkent Institute of Finance

Abstract

Crises are one of the indispensable laws of the creation and development of society, the occurrence of which is a characteristic feature of society. The first 20 years of the twenty-first century are characterized by events such as the crisis, epidemic and pandemic, which caused a lot of anxiety and financial losses for the world economy and society.

It is known that the crisis (chaos) occurs as a result of violation of the principles of functioning of the system that is operated. As a result of the actions taken to eliminate these violations and improve the functioning of the system, a more active, partially updated or fully effective new system can be formed from the existing system.

In connection with the Covid - 19 pandemic, the introduction, withdrawal, ban on all types of international flights, as well as restrictions imposed on production, trade, and service activities, caused a sharp decline in economic growth, employment, and income. The negative consequences of the Covid - 19 pandemic for important sectors of the world economy are described.

Keywords: Crisis, Economic Crisis, Covid-19, Covid - 19 Pandemic, Economy, Economic Sectors, Economic Growth, Economic Security, Negative Impact of The Pandemic, Negative Consequences of The Pandemic, Negative Impact of The Pandemic, Elimination of The Negative Consequences of The Pandemic.

INTRODUCTION

Crises are one of the indispensable laws of the creation and development of society, the occurrence of which is a characteristic feature of society. These are socio-economic phenomena that occur at different stages of the life of the state, society and the individual, the life cycle.

The first 20 years of the twenty-first century are characterized by events such as the crisis, epidemic and pandemic, which caused great concern to the world economy and society, as well as financial losses. The question of discussing the causes of the object and the subject of its occurrence, as well as the conclusion about the culprits, is the task of political scientists. Scientists and practitioners need to assess the impact of such events on the economic growth of countries, population growth and economic security of the country, as well as the scientific justification for ways to eliminate their consequences.

The crisis is a reality that damages the common values, socio-economic interests and goals of society and cannot be eliminated on the basis of existing concessions and commitments. There are exogenous and endogenous factors that cause each crisis situation, and to eliminate them, it is necessary to determine their nature and characteristics.

Content-based crises: economic, political, social, environmental, by scale: sectoral, territorial (one local territory, one state), are divided into state and world crises. It is also characterized by such types of crises as periodic, intermediate, structural, private, and sector crises.

It is known that as a result of a crisis, chaos (disorder) arises as a result of a violation of the principles of the functioning of the system that functions at the same time. As a result of the actions taken to eliminate these violations and improve the functioning of the system, a more active, partially updated or fully effective new system can be formed from the existing system. As

a result, the crisis acts as a motivating factor for the development of society (sphere).

Economic crises that occurred during periods of development of the personality of society, and their causes have always been studied by scientists and researchers. As a result of the conducted research, it is noted that the periods in which crises occur are cyclical in nature and it is possible to predict when they will occur. Based on the economic and mathematical analysis of economic crises that have occurred since the XVIII century, it was also found that there are certain general patterns in their occurrence and occurrence (Shcherbakov, 2018)

It is known that such indicators as the level of economic growth in the structure of the production system, economic, socio-economic indicators reflecting the state of development of the state, the level of budget revenues and population, inflation, external debt, unemployment, consumption volume, are indicators that reflect the level of economic security of the country. Crises also have a negative impact on these indicators, which ensure the security of the country. As a result, along with the standard of living of the population, the level of economic security of the country is also decreasing.

Although the COVID-19 pandemic, the high level of its danger, the rapid development of the human body and the occurrence of negative extremely severe consequences forced states to take drastic quarantine measures, quickly issued by the onset of the economic crisis around the world.

The COVID-19 pandemic, conducted by researchers from the Oxford University's Future of Humanity Institute, was also published in a long-term outlook for 150 countries. Preventive measures against coronavirus are divided into the following 4 categories.

1. Quit fighting the coronavirus in its own state.

2. Reduction in the rate of spread of coronavirus by 20 %, moderate quarantine, 35-50 % in human isolation, border closure, traffic restrictions.

3. Reducing the rate of spread of the coronavirus by 50 %, full quarantine, 65-80 % in isolation of a person, going out only if necessary, mass testing, closing borders, restricting traffic.

4. Reduction in the rate of spread of the coronavirus by 80 %, emergency quarantine, 90-95 % of people are isolated, access to the street is prohibited, mass testing, traffic is completely restricted.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, these countries have introduced these measures in the country due to the current situation. The measures applied have served to reduce the prevalence of the pandemic and have shown humanity the need to improve the system of measures used in emergency situations.

The well-known expert Yaroslav Bihovsky admits that the extreme measures that are useful for the Chinese state against the spread of the coronavirus have brought positive results, such as the development of digital management, mass and rapid blocking, control over the wearing of masks by 1.5 billion people, studying how the country adheres to hygiene, achieving a legislative ban on drug use.

In this article, an assessment of the origins of economic crises, their socio-economic status of countries and the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the world economy will be given. The issues studied as a result of the study and the opinions on how to eliminate their effects are stated in the research findings.

Materials and methods. For the purpose of research, the views of local and foreign scholars, government agencies, Internet sites are used to study the topic, and methods such as systematic analysis, comparative analysis, grouping are used to develop appropriate recommendations for solving existing problems.

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Literature Review. Economic crises are not a phenomenon that entered the life of society yesterday or today. Even in the life of the states before our era, there were economic crises, but at that time they were observed in some derivative countries due to the lack of globalization in the state economy.

But as a result of the development and globalization of economic relations between the countries of the world, which began in the XIX century, the world economy was formed. As a result, there are countries that influence the world economy. Changes in the economies of these countries began to affect the economies of both developed and developing countries.

A review of the literature of economic crises, the causes and consequences of which they originate,

shows that the adherents of this phenomenon are very different. In the works of J. Sismondi, K. Rodbertus-Jagetzow and T. Malthus, one can see studies of the nature of economic crises, as well as the periods of their occurrence. The problems of economic crises are fundamentally studied by Karl Marx. As a result of Marx's research, the causes of crises are justified by their validity from a scientific point of view and measures for their resolution are proposed (Marx, 1978).

Representatives of the classical theory of economic development A. Smith, D. Ricardo, A. Marshals believed that the market economy is still in a state of economic decline due to the regulation of supply and demand. But G. Malthus and S. Sismondi, in contrast to the proponents of the classical theory of the fattened, recognize that crises are inherent in any economy (Ros-sik, 2010).

The American economist J. Galbraith explains the psychological causes of crises by expecting a positive result, that is, as a result of optimistic views on the state of growth of stocks, real estate and products in the market, such a phenomenon as the bursting of the bubble in the economy (Galbraith, 2009). In contrast to these views, N. D. Kondratiev assesses crises as a recurring phenomenon in the 50s and 60s with the development of innovations and technologies in society (Kondratiev, 2002).

DISCUSSIONS.

1. THE IMPACT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON THE WORLD ECONOMY.

1.1 GENERAL AND PARTICULAR ASPECTS OF THE EMERGENCE OF ECONOMIC CRISES

In the XX and XXI centuries, many studies were conducted on the economic crises that occurred in the life of the individual society, the causes and patterns of their occurrence, as well as the elimination of their consequences. The results of these studies and the analysis of the causes of their occurrence indicate that the countries of the world are experiencing economic and technological development, the scale of economic crises, the negative impact on the economic situation of the population and countries, and the growing level of economic integration processes.

When studying the concept of crisis, two methods of comparison and an abstract-logical one are mainly used.

Comparison method is a method is based on the identification of significant and insignificant features of the one-of-a-kind and various aspects of the subject being studied. The same and different aspects of the crisis, which are determined on the basis of these signs, are compared with each other, and they are evaluated by their own legislation.

Abstract-logical method is a method of studying the essence of a phenomenon and processes by abstract logical reasoning. Abstraction is a distraction or removal from certain characteristics of the objects under study. The situation is studied by dividing the parts, they are the study of the essence of the phenomenon and processes by abstract logical reasoning.

The situation is first evaluated in its strengths and weaknesses, and the results are summarized by logical

conclusions based on the circumstances of the occurrence of macro level. Secondly, we study the conclusions, data on similar situations, and the results determined by the situation, on the basis of generalization, are reduced to a single conclusion.

As a result of studying the causes of macroeconomic crises A.A. Stopina and L. M. Korenyugina came to the conclusion that the crisis is not only characterized by the violation of economic structures, but also increase the chances of healing the economy, increase its resistance, and find the possibility of coexistence in the maintenance of the system (Stupina and Koreniugina, 2008).

A. V. Tarkhov believes that macroeconomic crisis provides for the development of an economic entity under the influence of his activities and the external environment associated with them, and organizational processes (Tarkhova, 2011).

The study of researchers' views on the crisis can be seen in their expert reviews that crises are one-sided, that is, they are evaluated according to those aspects that have passed since the first phase of the crisis. However, the fact that the crisis can arise not only because of the disruption of the system of economic relations, but also because of the Covid-19 pandemic or because of strong natural disasters, was overlooked by scientists.

There is also an opinion that the economic crisis is the result of unauthorized spending of funds in the state budget (Konopatov, 2012), the excess of production and trade volumes over the macroeconomic crisis (Petukhov, 2010), the violation of traditional economic relations and the tightening of the economic balance (Pogodina, 2004).

According to B. A. Reisberg, L.Sh Starodubtseva, "the economic crisis is a sharp decline in production, disruption of economic relations, deterioration of the economic situation of the country as a result of the banking system of enterprises, an increase in the number of unemployed, a decrease in the standard of living and social status of the population" (Reisberg, Lozovskii and Starodubtseva, 1997). Scholars such as A.B. Borisov, L.V. Vorontsova and P.N. Malyushkin, I.A. Maksimtsev, L.P. Kurakov, L.S. Tarasevich agree with this definition.

In our opinion, the main emphasis in the views of these researchers on the economic crisis is only on the origin of the crises. The aspects that influence economic changes after the crisis stages, in the definitions given above to economic crises, have been overlooked from the point of view of scientists. It can be seen that there are general patterns in the causes of crises that occurred before 2020 (Table 1).

Table 1.

Analysis of the causes and consequences of global economic crises

№	Years	Causes of the crisis	the states coverage	effects of the crisis
1	1857	The bankruptcy of the train companies the fall in stock prices	England, Germany, the USA, France	Production of pig iron in the United States by 20 %, and in Germany, 25% in France and 13%, France-17 %, Cotton consumption decreased by 27 %, 13 %, in Russia-by 14%.
2	1873-1878	Growth in the volume of loans and unjustified growth in real estate prices	Austria, Holland, Latin America, Germany, the USA	The volume of exports has sharply decreased, and state budget revenues have decreased.
3	1914	Sale of shares to foreign companies	France, Germany, the USA, Great Britain	Stock, commodity, and financial markets all contributed to this shortfall.
4	1920-1922	Post-war supply and demand imbalance	Denmark, Italy, Finland, Holland, Norway, the USA, Great Britain	Currencies depreciated and led to a reduction in production.
5	1929-1933	lack of stock markets	All countries except the USSR	Industrial production declined by 46% in the US, 24% in the UK, 41% in Germany, and 32% in France. The number of unemployed is more than 30 million.
6	1948-1949	Currency devaluation	The USA, the most of European countries, Japan	In the United States, the volume of production decreased by 83%. The number of unemployed increased by 139.5%.
7	1953-1954	The war in Korea	The USA, the most of European countries, Japan and Canada	In the capitalist countries, output fell by 9%, and the growth in the number of unemployed increased by 10 million.
8	1957-1958	Full economic hegemony transition to the USA	The USA, the most of European countries, Japan	Output fell by 13%, and the number of unemployed increased.

9	1960-1961	USA's export issues	The USA, England, Japan, Canada	Manufacturing capacity was decreased by 7 %
10	1966-1967	Extra money mass in the economy	The European countries, Japan	Manufacturing capacity was decreased by 8%
11.	1974-1975	The sharp rise in oil prices due to the Arab-Israeli war	Most European countries, the USA, Japan, Canada	Production volumes decreased by 13% in the United States, 20% in Japan, and 22% in Germany. The number of failed enterprises increased by 6% in the United States, 42% in Japan, and 40% in Germany compared to 1973. The number of unemployed in 1975 was 15 million people.
12	1979-1982	The rise in oil prices	Most European countries, the USA, Japan, Canada	Production declined by 8.2% in the United States and 1.2% in the European Union.
13	1990-1993	Currency devaluation		In Finland, GDP decreased by 13.0%, private investment-by 47%, consumption-by 11%. The unemployment rate rose from 3.5% to 13.5%.
14	1997	Devaluation of the national currencies	Asian countries	As a result of the crisis, GDP exceeded \$ 2 trillion.
15	2007-2009	Real estate and mortgage market mismatch	All countries of the world	The world's gross domestic product has declined, investment has increased by 25%, and 80% of the world's banks have a capital deficit.

Source: Prepared by the author based on Wikipedia

As a result of State measures aimed at eliminating the consequences of numerous economic crises that have occurred in the development of the world community, certain mechanisms have now developed. Based on the experience of overcoming the consequences of managing economic crises, such mechanisms for overcoming the consequences of crises as natural and state regulation have now been formed.

With the spontaneous method of crisis management, the state does not participate in the crisis process. Enterprises of the industry are steadily implementing measures to overcome the economic crisis. Therefore, economic crises can drag on for a long time.

As for the method of state regulation of the industry, financial, organizational and legal measures are used by the state to restore the activities of companies. The state's participation in measures to resolve the economic crisis makes it possible to reduce the duration of the crisis and quickly eliminate its consequences.

1.2. THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND THE GLOBAL ECONOMY

The first 20 years of the twenty-first century are characterized by such phenomena as crises, epidemics and pandemics, which caused a lot of anxiety and financial damage to the world economy and society. The discussion of the objective and subjective reasons for its occurrence and the question of the conclusion of the perpetrators is the task of political scientists. In connection with the need for scientists and practitioners to assess the impact of such phenomena on the economic growth of countries, the standard of living of the population and the level of economic security of the country and the scientific justification of ways to eliminate their consequences, it seems appropriate to study them from a socio-economic point of view.

There have been many crises in the history of the world economy, and only a few of them have affected

the world economy. A number of crises have affected the economies of individual states and territories. Yu. N. Enin, A. A. Piluttik studied the crises that have affected the global economy and overcome their consequences. In the course of their research, scientists note that of the 8 economic crises that occurred in 1948-1993, 5 are global, 2-territorial and 1-local in nature. But he believes that, although the scale is not high, all crises cause huge damage to the economic situation of the country (Enin,2014).

Karl Marx argues that crises consist of four stages: crisis, depression, rebirth, and recovery. Currently, the stages of depression, recovery, recovery, and recession recommended by the US National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER) are most commonly used in practice. NBER To assess the economic situation, it is recommended to use such indicators as GDP, personal income, unemployment rate, valuation, and industrial output.

The economic crisis of 1929-33, known in history as the Great Depression, which occurred in the United States and caused economic crises in many countries of the world, covered all sectors and countries of the world economy (except for the former USSR).

As a result of this crisis, the world's industrial production has declined by 46 per cent, steelmaking by 62 per cent, coal mining by 31 per cent, global consumption of goods has declined by 67 per cent, and the number of unemployed has reached 26 million people. Due to the negative impact of the crisis, the real income of the population decreased by 58%, the gross national product of the United States decreased by 1.85 times, and unemployment increased from 3.2% to 25%. About 135,000 firms and companies that went bankrupt as a result of the economic crisis reduced their income by 60%. As a result, the market capitalization decreased

from 87 billion dollars to 19 billion dollars, and its rate fell by 46% (Great Russian Encyclopedia).

The financial (1997-1998) and financial and economic crises (2008-2009), which are of a similar global nature, are among those crises that have caused enormous damage to the economies of almost all countries of the world.

Therefore, all countries of the world, in order to combat the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic, have imposed restrictions on the movement of people, transport and have taken measures to postpone all mass events indefinitely. International flights and trade turnover were restricted, the activities of economic entities and the issuance of interstate visas were temporarily suspended, and the 2020 Summer Olympic Games in Tokyo, Japan, were postponed to the summer of 2021.

We all know that measures to restrict the movement of people in society, transport and the postponement of all mass events for an indefinite period have an impact on the economy of countries and the income of the population. As a result of the measures taken by States, there is a sharp reduction in the volume of production and consumption in countries with large economies, the destruction of global production chains and trade links, sharp fluctuations in commodity prices and a deterioration in the global financial markets.

Maintaining social distance and restricting movement has not spared the education sector. As a result of the bans imposed on the education sector due to the pandemic, 90 % of students and 1.5 billion people in 19 countries were fired, students were forced to interrupt their studies (UNESCO, 2020)

Estimates show that the Covid-19 pandemic has caused much more damage to the global economy than the global financial and economic crisis of 2008. The number of people infected with the pandemic worldwide, as of February 12, 2021, is 108 million. 298 thousand 371 people. Due to the high risk of infection and the uncertainty of measures to prevent it, the rate of staff layoffs has increased dramatically. In the United States alone, between February and March 19, 2020, the unemployment rate rose from 3.5 % to 20 %, resulting in about 26 million people applying for unemployment benefits (Kondratiev, 2020).

International organizations estimate that in 2020, the number of people working in the informal economy will exceed 2 billion people who account for 62% of the world's working people. 90% of people working in the informal sector are citizens of low-income countries (ILO, 2018).

The International Monetary Fund (IMF) estimates that the global economy is projected to grow by 4% in 2020. After restrictions imposed in the United States in connection with the Covid-19 pandemic by various rating agencies, economists predicted that the rate of economic growth worldwide would decline by 3-6 % by the end of 2020. It was also noted that in some countries this amount may be higher than the global average, including the economic growth rate may decrease by 9.5 % in Italy, 14 % in the UK and 5.9 % in the US (Kondratiev, 2020).

Experts of the International economic forum note that the consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic may have a negative impact on the world economy within 3-5 years. A similar opinion was expressed based on the results of surveys with representatives of business and other social strata.

From the results of studies of the content of economic crises, their consequences and ways to overcome them, it is clear that the causes of the crises caused the destabilization of the socio-economic situation in countries, whether it was a natural disaster, an environmental disaster, an epidemic or a violation of the proportionality of economic relations. Therefore, efforts to prevent the occurrence of crises have always been the focus of economists, business representatives and politicians. But, despite the conclusions and suggestions of the conducted research, in the conditions of the economic crisis, there is no single solution to reduce its negative consequences.

The negative effects of the global crisis caused by the pandemic Covid-19, such as damage to the performance of the sectors of the economy, an increase in the deficit of the budgets of States, the rise in unemployment and a decline in living standards of the population, and the growth of poverty, define the importance of research for the solution of existing problems in this area.

The International Monetary Fund has released its positive forecasts for the expected economic growth of the world's economies for 2020. But the rapid and large-scale spread of the Covid-19 pandemic across the world has led to the need to revise the forecasts of all world agencies.

As a result of the impact of the restrictions imposed in connection with the pandemic on the economic growth rates of the developed countries of the world, the GDP volume has undergone negative changes in countries other than China (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1.

The impact of COVID-19 on the economic growth rates of major countries around the world (IMF, 2021)

International banking analysis predicts that by 2020, economic growth in developed countries will decline by 7%, in developing countries by 2.5%, and per capita income will fall by 3.6%, leading millions to poverty. The slowdown in the growth rate of the developed country's economy as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic was 3.6 percent in the United States and the eurozone, and 5.3 percent in Japan.

According to Coface's risk management analysis, the pandemic slowed economic growth to 18.5 percent

in Italy, 14.1 percent in Portugal, 13.1 percent in France, 5.1 percent in Lithuania, 7.5 percent in Latvia and 8.4 percent in the Czech Republic.

Internal and external restrictions imposed by the countries in connection with the pandemic have also had a negative impact on the activities of important sectors of the economy, such as automobiles, aerospace, construction, chemicals. (Figure 1.2).

Figure 1.2. The impact of COVID-19 on the real sector of the world economy (Impact of COVID-19 on Various Industries, May 18, 2020. Lucintel.)

It is predicted that the economic crisis caused by the pandemic will affect the sectors of the economy of all countries also in 2021, and economic growth will fully recover in 2024.

Analysts at KPMG, one of the world's top four audit firms, recommend dividing the impact of the pandemic on the economy into "short-term" and "long-term."

Short-term effects of the pandemic:

- Restrictions on the export of medical devices and protective equipment;
- Logistical problems;
- A decrease in demand;
- Change of the initial business strategy.

While the long-term effects of the pandemic:

- Tightening of the policy of admission of medical devices;
- Increased incentives for countries to buy their products on the domestic market;
- Manufacturers should strive to increase the number of their suppliers and strengthen control over transport and logistics risks;
- Strengthening the transition to a quick choice of a flexible storage system.

Industries most affected by the Covid-19 pandemic:

- Tourism and hospitality, catering;
- Foreign trade;
- Transport and logistics;
- Fitness, sports, cinema, theater, household services;
- The real sector.

Since the activities of these sectors are based on an offline service, the quarantine measures imposed due to the pandemic have caused them to be severely affected.

The following industries, which are not related to offline services, were not affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, but on the contrary, there was an increase in their activities.

- E-commerce;
- Online entertainment services (YouTube, streaming services);
- Production and sale of medical products;
- Remote medicine (MedTech);
- Services for the delivery of products.

An objective assessment of the consequences of the crisis in the world economy caused by the Covid-19 pandemic also requires a special analysis of the activities of the real sector of the economy. Because, as mentioned earlier, there are also activities that achieved economic growth during the pandemic. Therefore, we will also consider the impact of the pandemic on the activities of the real sectors of the economy.

1.3. IMPACT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON AIRLINE OPERATIONS

The main activities of the airline are the implementation of air transportation to the population and the provision of services for the transportation of goods of individuals and legal entities. According to the International Air Transport Association (IATA), 290 airlines in the world perform 82% of air transportation.

Worldwide, air passenger service increased by 7.8% in 2018, and by 4.2% in 2019. As for ensuring the state of completeness of air transport, in 2019 it increased by 0.7% compared to 2018, reaching a maximum of 82.6%. The volume of demand for air transportation exceeded the capacity of airlines by 3.4%.

Airlines have achieved an increase in the overall level of service by improving the quality of services provided and passenger transportation services in all countries of the world.

According to the results of 2019, an increase in the traffic mileage indicator was achieved in all regions. The growth rate compared to 2018 was 4.9% in Africa, 4.8% in Asia and the Pacific, 4.2% in Europe and Latin America, 2.4% in the Middle East and 4.1% in North America.

Passenger traffic on international routes increased by 7.1% in 2018, and by 4.1% in 2019. The level of aircraft occupancy in this direction increased by 0.8% and amounted to 82%.

The temporary suspension of international and domestic flights and the issuance of interstate visas in connection with the pandemic primarily affected the activities of airlines. According to the International Air Transport Association, the 10 largest airlines in the world with the S & P 500 index lost \$ 1.4 trillion due to the pandemic. All countries have also taken measures to support airlines. € 173 billion was allocated in the United States to support airlines. Financial support in the amount of US dollars only saved them from bankruptcy. Airlines cut 2020 due to the pandemic to 118.5 billion \$. As a result, with a loss of dollars. The level of such key performance indicators of airlines as passenger traffic, expenses and passenger traffic has sharply decreased.

8 American airlines have asked the government to allocate \$ 19 billion to prevent economic difficulties and bankruptcy caused by the shutdown of their operations due to restrictions imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic. The restrictions imposed by countries in connection with the pandemic led to the forced suspension of air traffic and a sharp decline in the performance of airlines (Figure 1.3).

Figure 1.3. The state of air travel and airline losses as a result of COVID-19 (IATA, 2021)

In 2020, the POS flow rate declined by 70 % in European countries, 72 % in Africa, and 73 % in the Middle East. In addition, the IATA organization recognizes that in 2020, compared to 2019, the demand for air transportation fell by 75.6 %, and the occupancy rate-by 58.1 %.

According to the forecasts of the International Air Transport Association, in 2021, the airlines of European countries will remain in the zone of the greatest losses and will receive 11.9 billion dollars a year. It is predicted that this may result in a loss in US dollars.

1.4. THE IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON THE FINANCIAL MARKET

One of the areas where the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic is most rapidly and vividly manifested is the global stock exchanges. At the beginning of 2020, the US stock exchanges reached their peak. The level of capitalization of the stock market is 156 % of GDP, which is a record high. As long as the pandemic does not have a negative impact on the stock markets, the volume of world trade will be \$ 88 trillion. This is equivalent to the total GDP of the countries of the world.

On the exchanges from February 20 to March 19, 2020, the S&P Dow Jones index fell 20 %, the S&P 500 index fell 28 %, the FTSE 250 index fell 41.3 %, and the Nikkei index fell 29 %. Also during this period, the share prices of the world's largest banks on the stock exchanges fell sharply.

In particular, there was a decrease in the share price of corporation Citigroup by 49%, Jay-Pi Morgan Chase-by 38%, Barclays Asia-by 52%.

The Dow fell 18.2 % as Boeing's share price fell 5.9 %, while the MSCI All-Country World index fell 1.9 %.

According to the Vice president of the consulting firm Deloitte, the value of 139 companies with a capitalization of more than ten billion dollars due to the pandemic has fallen by 20% compared to their prices before the introduction of quarantine measures related

to the coronavirus. The P/E (price/earnings) ratio on the S&P500 stock exchange fell from 21 to 12.7 due to the impact of the crisis.

M. Belyaev, an expert at the Russian Institute for Strategic Studies, believes that the world stock exchanges are the most affected by the coronavirus. It is estimated that the total amount of losses of stock exchanges worldwide is \$ 7 trillion dollars.

1.5. COVID-19 AND THE NATIONAL DEBT.

The state external debt is the funds raised from foreign funds, banks, and private investors in order to improve the economic climate in the country, and to finance social and special state programs. The external debt of states is characterized as follows:

* corporate external debt-financial obligations of economic entities attracted by mutual agreement from foreign entities;

* public external debt – a set of available financial liabilities for funds raised by authorized state bodies from foreign organizations, including guarantees provided for private sector debts;

* current external debt – a financial liability that must be repaid within 12 months;

* total public debt is the sum of the current and long-term internal and external financial obligations of the state.

The state external debt is characterized by an additional burden on the economy, which contributes to an increase in the country's domestic consumption and the implementation of social programs. Including:

* creates conditions for preferential use of debtors' resources;

• a high percentage is responsible for paying back the debt;

* availability of opportunities for the payment of the debtor's rights;

* negative assessment of debt growth in international ratings.

In world practice, the external debt position of the state is estimated by the percentage of debt to GDP. If

the amount of debt reaches the level of 30% of GDP, most states will limit borrowing.

The analysis of the effects of Covid-19 infection on the economy of our country shows that the indicators of the level of economic security also had a negative impact on the threshold values. Scholars are of the opinion that 30-150 indicators should be set as threshold indicators determining the level of economic security of the country (Isroilov, Abduganiyev and Ibragimov, 2020).

The International Monetary Bank recommends that the external debt rate of countries with lower-middle-income populations should not exceed 34% (Isroilov and Mukhammadiev, 2020). The growth of public and corporate external debt, dependence on imports and a high share of raw materials in the export structure are external factors affecting the country's economic security. As a result, these circumstances have a negative impact on the level of development of the country.

The International Monetary Fund noted that the public debt of developed countries increased from 104 to 124 % of GDP, while in developing countries—from 52 to 61 %.

1.6. MEASURES TO ELIMINATE THE CONSEQUENCES OF COVID-19

The measures taken by all States in connection with the Covid-19 pandemic in order to ensure the economic security of the country and eliminate its consequences can be divided into four groups.

1. Monetary measures.
2. Fiscal measures.
3. Health-improving measures.
4. Measures to control human activity.

All countries have adopted a number of legal acts concerning the measures taken in these areas and their application.

The Australian government will approve the response to the pandemic on March 12, 2020. According to the adopted document it is 213.6 billion US dollars. The Australian dollar (11% of GDP) overcame the effects of the pandemic, collecting 320 billion rubles. Australia planned to spend the dollar amount on a government guarantee. In order to eliminate unemployment for small businesses, the annual turnover amounted to 50 million US dollars. A grant of between AUD \$ 20,000 and AUD \$ 100,000 is provided for the payment of wages to entrepreneurs of up to AUD \$ 20,000, and for small businesses that have retained their jobs, a quarterly subsidy of AUD \$ 7,000 per employee is provided.

The UK government has allocated an additional \$ 12 billion to support the population and businesses and 18 billion pounds to fund long-term measures. 50 billion pounds together with other measures (2.3% of GDP) approved the redirection plan. In addition, in the context of the crisis, small and medium-sized businesses need to allocate 330 billion pound sterling (GDP 15 %)

The USA provided an additional \$ 2 trillion dollars to support the economy and the population. As a result of the appropriations, the amount of budget expenditures exceeded \$ 4 trillion from the revenue side of the budget, which has not been observed since 1945.

Germany's GDP being equal to 4.5%, 156 billion euro was used to eliminate the consequences of the pandemic. As a result of the measures taken, for the first time since 2013, the debt was raised, and the amount of public debt exceeded the norm established by regional legislation. Therefore, in Germany, the pandemic was recognized as an optional situation. The total amount of funds allocated to the state budget, the population and business entities is 1.1 trillion dollars.

Spain has allocated 17 billion euros. 200 billion \$ are in guaranteed provision of the public and private sectors. The amount of funds allocated to support the economy in euros is a total of 217 billion euros.

France has allocated 45 billion euros from the budget, subsidized and provided 300 billion euros to enterprises and guaranteed the allocation of a bank loan. The decline in the level of economic growth in France was 13.1 % for the first time since the Second World War.

The South Korean government has allocated an additional 10.9 billion won (13 billion won). The country's public debt reached 41.2% of GDP and amounted to 10.3 trillion US dollars to cover budget expenditures, a treasury bond was issued.

The Italian government in March 2020 presented the parliament with a budget deficit of 6.3 billion euros (2.5% of GDP) in total, and 25 billion \$. The law on the issue of Eurobonds was introduced. In Italy, the economic growth rate decreased by 13.5%.

Australia has committed \$ 213.6 billion to fund the costs of the pandemic (11 %of GDP allocated funds from the central budget in the amount of 320 billion Australian dollars (16.4 per cent of GDP).

Countries such as the Netherlands, Denmark, Poland, Portugal, Ireland, the Czech Republic, Austria, Greece, Sweden and Estonia have allocated funds to deal with the consequences of the pandemic in the amount of 2 to 10 percent of GDP (ECONOMY AND LIFE, 2020).

The Government of Uzbekistan has taken a number of measures to mitigate the negative impact of the pandemic on the economy of society and the state, as well as to support the activities of the population and business entities. In particular, the presidential decree of March 19, 2020 "On priority measures to mitigate the negative impact of the coronavirus pandemic and global crisis situations on economic sectors " defines measures aimed at ensuring macroeconomic stability, uninterrupted operation of industries, economic sectors and social support for the population during the fight against the widespread spread of the coronavirus pandemic and other global risks (Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan 5969, 2020)

The measures prescribed in the decree to mitigate the negative impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the economy, support the population and business entities in quarantine, can be divided into the following three groups:

- population and economic entities
- organizational support mechanisms;
- tax mechanisms to support the population and business entities;
- credit mechanisms to support business entities.

Also, according to the decree, 1 billion US dollars will be paid at the expense of budget and external

In the first half of 2020, under the influence of the negative effects of Covid-19, Kazakhstan experienced a decline in GDP by 1.8 %, Kyrgyzstan-by 5.3 %, and the Russian Federation-by 9.5-10 %.

The negative impact of the economic crisis caused by Covid-19 on the economies of the countries is also reflected in the decline in investment volumes. According to international financial organizations, the volume of foreign direct investment in tourism in 2020 is expected to increase by 40% compared to 2019, and in 2021-by 5-10%.

Uzbekistan also experienced the negative impact of the economic crisis caused by the Covid-19 pandemic. From the Anti-Crisis Fund, 360 million US dollars were allocated for investment projects in order to create new jobs. The volume of investments in the first

half of 2019 compared to 2020 decreased by 12.8%, despite the additional direction of funds from the United States.

It is known from research that the reduction of budget revenues due to crises and the increase in the level of budget deficits negatively affect the implementation of state programs (Isroilov, Ibragimov and Pardaev, 2020).

As a result of the measures taken to mitigate the consequences of the pandemic in 2020, in Uzbekistan, along with the growth of GDP, the average growth rate of prices for basic food products was 15.3 %. In particular, potatoes rose in price – by 42%, eggs-by 38%, vegetable oil-by 27%, sugar-by 21%, meat products - by 18.1% and bakery products - by 15.2%. According to Tradingeconomics, the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Uzbekistan expanded 1.60 percent in 2020. (Figure 1.4) The inflation rate for the population increased by 17-18 %, for business entities-by 18-19 %.

Figure 1.4. Uzbekistan GDP Annual Growth Rate (TRADINGECONOMICS.COM, 2021)

2. NEGATIVE IMPACT OF THE CORONAVIRUS CRISIS ON THE TOURISM SECTOR

2.1 THE ROLE OF TOURISM IN THE GLOBAL ECONOMY.

Tourism in the economy of states due to the fact that it is currently considered the main source of development in many countries of the world and is a multi-faceted industry:

- forms the basis of gross domestic product (GDP);
- provides employment for the population;
- creates new jobs;

- serves as the main source of the foreign trade balance

Due to these economic factors, many countries of the world are currently paying great attention to the development of the tourism industry in order to develop the economy, provide employment for the population and bring information about the spiritual and cultural heritage of the country to the world population. Data from the International Tourism Organization (UNWTO) show that tourism now accounts for 10% of global GDP, and in some countries-20% of GDP (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1. The top ten countries by the share of tourism in the GDP structure.
(Prepared by the author based on <https://knoema.com>, 2021)

The tourism sector also plays an important role in the countries' exports. In Palau, 90% of the country's exports, in Africa, 10% is formed by tourist products. Special attention is paid to the role of tourism in ensuring the implementation of the 8th, 12th and 14th "sustainable development programs" Of the United Nations.

Along with the development of the tourism sector, the related areas of transport, hotel business, road construction, national crafts and national culture will also develop, which will contribute to the creation of new jobs. Tourism in the world also plays an important role in the share of countries' exports, and the industry's share in world trade in 2019 was 7 percent. Currently, there are 217 tourist destinations in the world, which, according to the forecasts of the International Tourism Organization, was expected to amount to 1 billion 600 people traveling to these destinations, as well as the industry's revenues, amount to about \$ 2 trillion worldwide in 2020.

2.2. TOURISM AND EPIDEMICS

Tourism has also experienced all kinds of political, economic, social, political, environmental, and infectious diseases (Ebola, Zika) that humanity has encountered along with other industries. An analysis of trends in the number of international tourists worldwide in 1950-2018 showed that tourist flows are influenced by factors of distance and the source of the epidemic (Fig. In cases where the negative impact of the epidemic on human health was significant, the number of tourists decreased, but, conversely, when the damage was low and the distance was large, the number of tourists did not change much. For example, - SARS from the picture (2002) and H1N1 (2009), it can be seen that the negative impact of such epidemics on tourism activities was high. As a result of loss of constituent entities of the tourism industry was also consistent with these trends. (Figure 2.2.)

Figure 2.2. International tourist arrivals by region of the world 1950-2018 (Marinko Škare, 2021)

Studies have shown that the global tourism industry declined by 57 million tourists as a result of epidemics in 1989-2019, and tourism spending during this period amounted to 95 billion \$ and suffered losses in the amount of 2 billion US dollars (Škare, 2021).

However, while tourism is an industry that has withstood the impact of such crises, it has found itself in a state of economic paralysis, unable to cope with the extremely dangerous and rapidly spreading characteristics and consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic. Because, as already mentioned, the flow of tourists is affected by the type and distance of the epidemic. The Covid-19 pandemic has brought the tourism industry and all related industries to a complete standstill.

2.3. TOURISM AND COVID-19

Unlike other sectors of the economy, the tourism industry has faced many difficulties due to the restrictions imposed in connection with the pandemic. For example, the agricultural sector continued to operate in compliance with certain requirements in order to avoid interruptions in the supply of food to the population, even during the period of easing of restrictions.

Similarly, the food, medical devices, medicines, and medical protective equipment industries have also been given the opportunity to continue their activities in the context of the pandemic, in accordance with the requirements established under the quarantine. Food trading, e-commerce, medical products and medicines trading, as well as remote medical and online telemedicine services also worked and achieved a certain level of economic growth.

Full and partial restrictions imposed in almost all countries of the world in connection with the pandemic have led to a halt in the production, trade, services, and tourism activities. In 2020, due to the pandemic, the tourism sector will account for \$ 2.2 trillion in global GDP. US\$, or 2.8 %. As a result of the restrictions imposed in the countries, 120 million people work in the tourism sector worldwide. the number of tourists decreased by 56 % compared to 2020 due to the fact that

people became unemployed and stopped air, rail and road services.

According to the UNWTO, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, 93 (43 %) of the 217 existing tourist destinations in the world were completely closed to international tourism. 83% of these tourist destinations are completely banned in Europe, 80% in the Americas, 70% in the Asia-Pacific region, 62% in the Middle East, and 57% in Africa. The revenues of the subjects of the sphere for 5 months of 2020 will amount to 320 billion US dollars. The amount of this damage is 3 times higher than the damage caused to the industry as a result of the global financial and economic crisis of 2008.

From year to year, the tourism sector is becoming increasingly important in the development of the economy of many countries around the world. The increase in the types and quality of tourist products and services is one of the main factors contributing to the further development of international tourism. The tourism industry in France, Spain, the United States, China, Italy, Turkey, Mexico, Germany, Thailand and the United Kingdom has been hit hard by bans and restrictions imposed in the wake of the pandemic Covid-19.

Spain is considered one of the countries whose economy is more dependent on the tourism sector. In the rating of competitiveness in the field of tourism, determined by the organization "World Economic Forum", the Spanish state has been ranked 1st since 2015. Thanks to the positive results of the trends in the development of the tourism industry in the economy of the Spanish state in 2018, 12.3% of GDP was formed at the expense of the tourism industry. In 2015-2018, the revenues of the tourism industry increased by 25.3 % and by 11.8 % in GDP. Due to the development of international tourism in 2016-2019, the flow of foreign tourists visiting the countries increased by 11.13 %. 48.28% of the flow of foreign tourists who visited Spain was accounted for by the United Kingdom, Germany, and France (INE, 2020).

In the field of tourism, hotel management is an industry that plays an important role. In 2019, 65.38% of

tourists who visited Spain lived in hotels for an average of 3.08 days. Another entity that has suffered in the tourism sector from the restrictions and prohibitions imposed due to the pandemic is the hotel industry.

According to the estimates of Cushman & Wakefield, due to restrictions and bans on entry and exit from the countries in the 1st half of 2020, hotel revenues in St. Petersburg decreased by 79 %, Prague-by 73.6 %, Rome – by 73.3 %.

Developed countries such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia, and Switzerland have introduced measures such as hotel tax cuts, wage subsidies, and concessional lending. As a result, hotel managers took steps not to fire employees in exchange for a reduction in wages.

Despite the fact that the Event industry is a new direction in the global economy, it has found its place in the life of society and continues to develop. By the end of 2018, more than 180 billion people took part in the events organized by the industry. a person from 1.5 countries. The annual turnover of the industry's enterprises is 1.07 billion US dollars, the subjects of this direction employed up to \$ 10.3 million people and the GDP per capita was 62.14 billion dollars around the world.

Internal and external restrictions on movement and social distancing imposed in countries due to the Covid-19 pandemic have led to a decline in the performance of Event industry actors.

Information on the results of research conducted by the R&K Fair research center in March-April 2020 with the participation of partners shows that 17,000 employees work in the Event industry all over Russia on a permanent basis, and 25,000 with attracted employees.

The annual volume of trade turnover of the subjects of the sphere in 2019 amounted to 160 billion US dollars. Only the subjects of the Event industry across Russia ended 2020 with a loss of 110 billion rubles and were forced to cut 50% of jobs.

CONCLUSION

The society has experienced a huge number of natural disasters and infections, as well as economic crises. Each negative case has left its consequences in the history of mankind. The wisdom bestowed on humanity by the great creator has served each time to get rid of natural disasters and infections and to find ways to move society to the next stage of development.

The lessons of the COVID-19 pandemic show the politicians and leaders of the developed world the need to abandon the desire to be the only hegemon in the world. Because the desire to be the only hegemon in the world encourages states to use the wrong rule “any method can be used to win”.

The exact causes and secrets of coronavirus infection will be revealed in the coming years. But history does not forget its consequences for humanity. Lost opportunities to improve the lives of people and society who died prematurely due to the virus cannot be recovered. The lessons of the pandemic show us that we must look at the world more tolerantly.

Overcoming the consequences of the economic crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic requires the self-control of all States. Because of the pandemic, the

pace of economic development around the world has slowed down for 10 years. Compensating for this period is the first necessity of expanding self-regulation.

The development of the countries of the world requires taking measures to coordinate the levels of targeted budget allocation and reduce the share of administrative expenses in accordance with the recommendations justified by scientists as a result of the analysis of economic trends and practices.

In order to support the sectors of the economy, it will be necessary to extend the duration of the measures taken during the pandemic to optimize the tax burden in the state-fiscal and monitoring policies. Extending the terms of these measures will help prevent the population from falling into poverty and increase the investment opportunities of business entities and citizens.

As a result, additional investment resources are formed for the development of the economy.

The COVID-19 pandemic has prompted countries that were cautious yesterday about digitizing the processes of socio-economic life to also step up their activities. The further development of society's life depends on the degree of its digitization and quality. Therefore, it is necessary that the processes of digitalization of all stages of the life of the state and society should be the priority directions of the economic policy of the states.

The development of special programs for the provision of online medical services and the introduction of artificial intelligence systems in the field of health care will improve the quality of medical services to the population in emergency situations, such as the pandemic COVID-19.

The development of special humanitarian assistance programs by international organizations in support of the digitalization processes of the least developed countries will serve for the large-scale implementation of this direction.

In our country, the issues of accelerated development of the tourism industry are given great attention as a positive factor that ensures economic growth, the formation of budget revenues, employment, foreign exchange earnings from the export of services. To prevent the negative impact of emergencies such as the Covid-19 pandemic on the economy:

- introduction of the use of artificial intelligence to ensure the control of legislative measures for emergency situations;
- improving the system of remote medical care and the use of artificial intelligence in medicine;
- increasing the availability of e-commerce and e-pharmacy services;
- development of mechanisms for the development of online education and improving its quality;
- increasing the use of artificial intelligence in the organization of hotel services;
- development of mobile applications for online health monitoring of foreign tourists;
- it is advisable to develop a program for the development of opportunities for creating and using an electronic tourist product.

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